

Studies in Sesquiterpenes—LIX Isolongifolene (Part 9) : Further Rearrangement[†]

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Isolongifolene under appropriate acid catalysis rearranges to a tetralin derivative. Taking into consideration the possible mechanism of this rearrangement, acid-catalyzed rearrangement of 8-bromoneoisolongifolene and 8-oxo-neoisolongifolene has been investigated when 1,1-dimethyl-7-isopropyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene and 4,4-dimethyl-6-isopropyl-7,8-dihydrotetralone respectively were obtained, as anticipated.

ISOLONGIFOLENE (1)¹, the acid-catalyzed rearrangement product of longifolene (2), is still a high-energy molecule due to the presence of the strained bicyclo-[2,2,1] heptane system², and hence, should be prone to further rearrangement under favourable conditions. In practice³, isolongifolene on being refluxed (5 hr) with Amberlyst-15⁴ or phosphoric acid-silica gel, yielded besides a polymer (25-30%), a liquid product consisting (GLC, PMR) essentially of an aromatic compound (~55%) and at least four other hydrocarbons (total ~45%), one predominating to the extent of over 60%. The same reaction products can be reached by using longifolene instead; and, when longifolene was exposed to these reagents under milder conditions (36 hr at 95°) isolongifolene ($\alpha_D - 22.6^\circ$; ~82% racemized¹) in over 95% yield was obtained. The transformation of longifolene (or isolongifolene) to these new products can be effected more conveniently with $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$; for example, addition of this reagent (3%) to longifolene (neat) at room temp. (~27°) results in an exothermic reaction leading to a product (after 14 hr at room temp.) essentially identical with that obtained with the above-mentioned reagents.

The aromatic hydrocarbon from the above reaction was best isolated either by preparative GLC or by treatment of the total mixture with perbenzoic acid, followed by column chromatography over Al_2O_3 . The compound analyses for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}$ (M^+ , m/e 202) and is clearly a benzene derivative^{5,6}: $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 277 nm (ϵ , 630),

267 nm (ϵ , 606); IR, aromatic absorption 1612, 1575, 891 and 820 cm^{-1} , possibly 1,2,4-trisubstituted⁶; PMR, three aromatic protons, 2H, partly overlapping singlets centred at 6.81 ppm and, 1H broadened singlet at 7.01 ppm. The PMR spectrum further shows signals assignable to: two tertiary Me's (6H, s, 1.27 ppm), one isopropyl group (6H, d, 1.21 ppm, $J=7$ Hz), three benzylic protons (3H envelop centred at 2.66 ppm), essentially a triplet overlapping a septet. These structural features, considered along with mechanistic reasoning (*vide infra*) for its genesis from isolongifolene, suggest its formulation as 3. This was readily confirmed, when Se dehydrogenation furnished eudalene (4)⁷ in good yield.

Conceivably, the transformation of 1 to 3 can be visualised as proceeding through 5 to 6 to the bicyclic cation 7, which by elimination followed by isomerisation-disproportionation⁸ results in the tetralin 3 and other hydrocarbons, which should be mostly mono-olefins. The major component of these non-tetralin hydrocarbons was separated by preparative GLC and further purified by chromatography over AgNO_3 -silica gel. The product $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}$ (M^+ , m/e 206) from its spectral data (*vide experimental*) is considered to be the expected mono-olefin 8.

Obviously, the conjugated diene(s) generated by 7, should be capable of interception, before disproportionation.

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donation, by a suitable dienophile. When isomerisation of isolongifolene was carried out in presence of maleic anhydride, a considerable yield of the adducted product (isolated as acids, after hydrolysis) was obtained, however, no pure compound could be isolated.

In view of the proposed mechanism for the isomerization of isolongifolene (1) to the tetralin 3, it appeared of interest to examine the action of acids on 8-bromoneoisolongifolene (9), readily available⁹ from the action of bromine on isolongifolene. On protonation, 9 (Fig. 1) should generate 10, which, unlike the system $5 \rightleftharpoons 6$, should display little tendency to isomerise to 11, which has an electron-withdrawing group on the α -carbon. Thus, 10 may be expected to readily fragment to 12, leading ultimately (Fig. 1) to the tetralin 3. A clue to such a transformation was obtained during the acetolysis¹⁰ of 9, when tetralin 3 was produced to the extent of 2-5%. In practice, treatment of bromide 9 with 90% H_2SO_4 aq at 0° led to rapid evolution of HBr gas to finally give tetralin 3 in a yield of 68%. Similarly, the corresponding chloride⁹ on exposure to 90% H_2SO_4 aq or $BF_3 \cdot Et_2O$ yielded 3 (55-62%) with generation of HCl gas.

Fig. 1. Possible route to tetralin 3 from 8-bromoneoisolongifolene

The above reasoning received additional support, when ketone 15¹¹ on exposure to 90% H_2SO_4 aq at $\sim 0^\circ$, rapidly (5 min) passed into the anticipated dienone 20 in over 75% yield. λ_{max}^{EtOH} 320 nm

Fig. 2. Acid-catalyzed rearrangement of 8-oxo-neoisolongifolene

(ϵ , 9985)¹². IR (liq.): $C=O$ ¹³ 1668, 1645 cm^{-1} ; $C=C$ ¹⁴ 1637, 1575 cm^{-1} . PMR (CCl_4): Me_2CH (6H, d, 1.10 ppm; $J=6.5$ Hz), two $Me-C$ (6H, s, 1.16 ppm), $C=CH$ (1H, s, 5.90 ppm). It should be noted that in this case also isomerization 16 $\rightarrow$ 17 is contra-indicated.

In view of the possible use of tetralin 3 as a starting material for synthesis of derivatives for possible perfumery use ('musk odour'),^{3a,15} isomerization of longifolene to tetralin has been studied by using reagents and methods that can be adopted for large-scale preparation. It will suffice to mention here that longifolene can be rearranged to the required compound 3 in yields of 30-35%, by vapour phase contact with catalysts such as chromia-alumina¹⁶ or molybdena-alumina¹⁷ at temperatures of 350-450°.

Experimental

All m.p.s and b.p.s are uncorrected. Light petroleum refers to fraction b.p. 60-80°. All solvent extracts were finally washed with brine and dried on (Na_2SO_4).

The following instruments were used for spectral/analytical data: Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer, model 267; Perkin-Elmer model R 32 (90 MHz) NMR spectrometer; Varian Mat CH 7 Mass spectrometer (70 eV, direct inlet system); Hewlett-packard 5712A and 7624A gas chromatographs (Al columns). All PMR spectra were taken in 15-20% soln in CCl_4 with TMS as internal reference.

Rearrangement of longifolene to tetralin 3

(i) *With 8.5% H_3PO_4 on silica gel.* Silica gel (100g; -30, +120 mesh) was mixed with H_3PO_4 aq (10 ml of 85% ortho-phosphoric acid diluted with 10 ml water) and the mixture mechanically rolled for 5 hr. After this the material was activated at 120°/2 hr.

Longifolene (17.8g; GLC purity >95%) and the above reagent (1.4g) were mixed and refluxed ($\sim 260^\circ$, N_2) for 1.5 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled, filtered to remove the catalyst, which was washed with ether (10 ml). The filtrate and washings were combined, freed of solvent and distilled to get a product (12.4 g): b.p. 100-108°/3.5 mm. GLC (10% Carbowax 20 M on 60-80 mesh Chromosorb-W; 0.6 cm $\times$ 360 cm; 160°; 60 ml H_2 /min): RRT 1 (7%), 1.8 (4%), 1.87 (32%), 2.45 (14%), 3.25 (4%), 3.45 (37%), 4.47 (2%).

(ii) *With Amberlyst-15⁴.* Longifolene (20 g) was refluxed with Amberlyst-15 resin (1 g) for 15 min, when the isomerisation was complete (GLC). It was worked up as above to give, after distillation, 18g of a liquid (b.p. 102-106°/3.5 mm) essentially identical (GLC) with the above product.

(iii) *With $BF_3 \cdot Et_2O$.* Longifolene (dried over Na; 200g) was taken in a suitable flask equipped with a reflux condenser and protected from moisture. To

this freshly distilled $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ (10 ml) was added in one lot with swirling, when the reaction mixture turned dark red with rapid rise in temperature to the point of reflux. After 24 hr the reaction mixture was diluted with C_6H_6 (200 ml), washed with Na_2CO_3 aq (10%, 100 ml $\times$ 2) and finally with brine. Solvent removal and distillation gave the product containing some 45% tetralin 3 : b.p. 102-106 $^\circ$ /3.5 mm, yield 141g.

1-1-Dimethyl-7-isopropyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene(3)

The rearranged product from any of the above reactions, was separated by preparative GLC (20% Carbowax 20M on 45-60 mesh Chromosorb-W; 0.93 cm $\times$ 360 cm Al column; 200 $^\circ$; 120 ml H_2 /min) to get pure material having RRT=3.45; b.p. 90-92 $^\circ$ /1mm; n_D^{20} 1.5092. IR (liq.): 1612, 1575, 1380, 1360, 1335, 1268, 1082, 1052, 967, 891, 863, 820, 803, 742 cm^{-1} . Mass: m/e 202 (M^+ , 42%), 187 (100%), 159 (14%), 145 (23%), 131 (18%), 119 (11%), 117 (11%), 107 (13%), 105 (14%), 91 (15%). (Found: C, 89.00; H, 11.29. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}$ requires: C, 89.04; H, 10.96%).

Dehydrogenation to eudalene (4)

A mixture of the above tetralin-containing hydrocarbon mixture (5 g), and Se metal (12 g) were heated at 300-310 $^\circ$ for 46 hr. The reaction mixture was extracted with light petroleum and the soln passed through a small column of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{I}$, which was washed with light petroleum (250 ml). Removal of solvent, followed by distillation of the residue furnished a yellowish liquid (3.95 g): b.p. 102-105 $^\circ$ /2 mm. This product (0.92 g) in EtOH (5 ml) was treated with a hot soln of trinitrobenzene (1.045 g) in 25 ml of EtOH, when on cooling to room temp ($\sim$ 25 $^\circ$), silky yellow needles (0.52 g; m.p. 110-11 $^\circ$) separated, which were recrystallized from EtOH: m.p. 112-113 $^\circ$ (0.42g), mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of trinitrobenzene complex of eudalene, was undepressed. Pure eudalene (4) was regenerated from this complex by the usual Al_2O_3 method¹⁸ and identified (IR, PMR) by comparison with an authentic sample¹⁸.

1,1-Dimethyl-7-isopropyl- $\Delta^{9,10}$ -octalin (8)

During the isolation of 3 by preparative GLC, the second major component (RRT=1.87) was also collected separately. This material on TLC (15% AgNO_3 on SiO_2 gel; solvent, hexane) showed, besides one major spot (R_f 0.64), three minor components. Hence, the product (180 mg) was chromatographed on a column (1.0 cm $\times$ 51 cm) of 15% AgNO_3 - SiO_2 gel. Hexane (10 ml $\times$ 4) eluted TLC pure material of R_f 0.64. Tetranitromethane (CHCl_3) test: deep yellow colour. UV(EtOH): end absorption, ϵ_{215} 2181, ϵ_{220} 1400, ϵ_{225} 825. IR (liq.): 1662, 1391, 1366, 1339, 1266, 1231, 1208, 1159, 1027 cm^{-1} . PMR: Me_2CH (6H, d, 0.90 ppm; $J=6.5$ Hz), two Me-C- (6H, s, 0.96 ppm). Mass: m/e 206 (M^+), 191, 177, 163, 135 (Found: C, 86.62; H, 12.76. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{24}$ requires: C, 87.30; H, 12.70%).

Rearrangement in presence of maleic anhydride

Isolongifolene (or longifolene; 12 g), 8.5% H_3PO_4 on silica gel (1 g) and maleic anhydride (6 g) were mixed and heated at 200-205 $^\circ$ for 3.5 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with ether (75 ml) and washed with tepid water (15 ml $\times$ 5) to remove unreacted maleic anhydride. The ether soln was freed of solvent and the residue (15.5 g) hydrolysed by refluxing with 10% NaOH alcoholic (15 g NaOH) for 3 hr. This was worked up in the usual manner into neutral ($\sim$ 2 g) and acid (dark brown foam, 13 g) fractions. A part of the acid was esterified (CH_2N_2) and distilled to get the dimethyl ester, b.p. 171-190 $^\circ$ /1 mm. This (1 g) was further, purified by chromatography over neutral $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{II}$ (1.5 cm $\times$ 18 cm) to get a "pure" cut eluted with 25% benzene in hexane: b.p. 155-160 $^\circ$ /0.2 mm, n_D^{20} 1.5005, mixture of isomers (PMR); IR (liq.): COOMe 1742, 1200 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 72.73; H, 9.37. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 71.96; H, 9.78%).

Action of sulphuric acid on 8-haloneoisolongifolene

8-Bromoneoisolongifolene (9; 1.4 g) was added in one lot to cooled (0 $^\circ$) 90% H_2SO_4 aq (v/v; 5 ml) with stirring. Evolution of HBr ceased after 5 min, when it was worked up by pouring into ice-water (25 ml) and extraction with hexane (15 ml $\times$ 3). The hexane extract was washed with 10% Na_2CO_3 aq (15 ml $\times$ 4), followed by water and brine. Solvent was removed to get a thick residue which on distillation furnished tetralin 3 (680 mg), b.p. 100-110 $^\circ$ (bath)/3 mm.

The corresponding 8-chloroneoisolongifolene (4.0g), when treated likewise furnished $\sim$ 2.0 g of tetralin 3.

Action on boron trifluoride on 8-chloroneoisolongifolene

A mixture of 8-chloroneoisolongifolene (3.0 g) and $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ (two drops) was stirred at 90-95 $^\circ$ for 3 hr, when evolution of HCl had ceased. The reaction mixture was diluted with hexane (40 ml) and worked up as above to yield after distillation 1.55 g of tetralin 3.

Rearrangement of 8-oxo-neoisolongifolene (15)

To 8-oxo-neoisolongifolene (5.0 g) at 0 $^\circ$, 90% H_2SO_4 aq. (v/v, 10 ml), also chilled to 0 $^\circ$, was introduced with stirring so that the temperature did not exceed 5 $^\circ$. Stirring was continued at 0-5 $^\circ$ for a total of 15 min, when the reaction mixture was poured into ice and the product taken up in hexane (40 ml $\times$ 3). The combined extract was washed with saturated Na_2CO_3 aq. (40 ml $\times$ 2), water (40 ml $\times$ 2), brine (40 ml) and dried. Solvent was flashed off to give a product (4.4 g), which was distilled to get a colourless liquid (4.1g), b.p. 140-145 $^\circ$ (bath)/2.5 mm. This product contained one major ($\sim$ 90%) component (GLC), which was isolated by preparative GLC (5% carbowax 20M on 60-80 mesh chromasorb-W; 0.93 cm $\times$ 180 cm Al column; 220 $^\circ$; 120 ml H_2 /min). Mass: m/e 218 (M^+ ;

90°/o) 201 (90°/o), 176 (83°/o), 175 (100°/o) 148 (65°/o), 131 (65°/o) 120 (55°/o) 105 (75°/o), 91 (55°/o). (Found: C, 82.00; H, 9.91. C₁₅H₂₂O requires: C, 82.51; H, 10.16°/o).

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